

Elcogen – Next Generation Solid Oxide Cell and Stack Technology

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Elcogen is one of the leading European manufacturers of solid oxide cell (SOC) technology. Elcogen products are unique combination of best in class performance and low-cost product structure. The unit cell and stack products are designed for low temperature operation enabling major cost reductions in the system level. Elcogen's operations are located in the Nordic-Baltic technology cluster of Finland and Estonia. This article summarizes the recent activities and development trends of Elcogen.

Introduction

Elcogen is currently focused in ramping up its unit cell and stack production with the increased customer requests. The short-term goal is to set-up of a demonstration manufacturing plant for the unit cells and stacks with annual capacity of 50 MW. To facilitate the goals, Elcogen has signed EUR 12 million loan facility with The European Investment Bank (EIB). The loan is the first in the Baltic countries to get support under the InnovFin – EU-finance for innovators programme, which is financed from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. Specifically, the financing falls under InnovFin's Energy Demonstration Projects (EDP) facility.

Elcogen is continuously developing its products for higher performance, longer lifetime, lower costs, increased quality and expanded applications. This article summarizes Elcogen's latest stack test results conducted to study for long-term stability, combined RedOx and thermocycle durability and manufacturing quality.

Elcogen stacks are built around company's internally manufactured unit cells. The unit cells are anode supported with cell structure combining anode contact layer (NiO, 2 μm), anode support layer (NiO/YSZ, 400 μm), anode functional layer (NiO/YSZ, 10 μm), electrolyte (YSZ, 3 μm), barrier layer (GDC, 2 μm), and cathode (LSC, 20 μm). The interconnect plates are manufactured from ferritic sheet metal and coated with MCO. The stack design for commercial application is called elcoStack[®] E3000 and the stack design for technology evaluation purposes elcoStack[®] E350. The difference between the design variants is the air supply means, i.e. elcoStack[®] E350 has fully manifolded air side structure as elcoStack[®] E3000 utilizes open air design. Figure 1 depicts elcoStack[®] E350 and elcoStack[®] E3000. The flow distribution and electrical contacting structures for both design variants are identical and thus the results obtained with both designs are directly comparable to each other. elcoStack[®] E350 design is easily integrable to most solid oxide fuel cell test stands and elcoStack[®] E3000 is optimized for large systems utilizing multiple stacks.

Figure 1. a) elcoStack® E350 with 15 unit layers, fully manifolded air structure, all unit layers equipped with voltage measurement cables and in-stack thermocouple. b) elcoStack® E3000 with 119 unit layers and open air structure.

Experimental Stack Results

Long-Term Stability

The long-term stability of elcoStack® is studied with steam reformed natural gas. The long-term stability experiment is conducted with standard elcoStack® material system and with 15 unit layers. The stack type in this test is elcoStack® E350. The gas composition is typical Finnish pipeline grade natural gas with lower heating value of 802.3kJ/mol ($[\text{CH}_4] = 98\%$, $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_6] = 0.8\%$, $[\text{C}_3\text{H}_8] = 0.2\%$, $[\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}] = 0.02\%$, $[\text{N}_2] = 0.9\%$, $[\text{CO}_2] = 0.1\%$). The odorant in natural gas, THT, is cleaned with a room temperature sorbent. Test is conducted at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd. Natural gas is mixed with steam feed prior the reformer reactor. The steam-to-natural gas ratio is 2.2. The gas composition fed to the stack is standardized in the test by controlling the outlet temperature of the steam reforming reactor to 600°C. The resulting composition for the stack inlet is $[\text{CH}_4] = 7\%$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}] = 26\%$, $[\text{CO}] = 7\%$, $[\text{H}_2] = 52\%$, $[\text{CO}_2] = 8\%$. Fuel utilization in the test is 60% simulating conditions of a system equipped with anode exhaust gas recycle unit. The fuel cell cathode is fed with preheated air. The oxygen utilization is 22%. Both the air and fuel are heated to 600°C for the stack inlet. Stack is located in a furnace with setpoint of 620°C. The current at the nominal operation conditions is 30 A.

Figure 2 a depicts the mean unit layer voltage as a function of operation time. Stack has been operated at constant steam reforming conditions 7800 hours and the test is still continued (May, 2019). The voltage decay over the whole operation time has been 0.4 %/1000h and the ASR decay 14 $\text{m}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2/1000\text{h}$. The voltage decay is determined as the slope divided by the intercept of linear regression of the mean unit layer voltage

measured at the nominal conditions. The ASR decay is determined as the slope of linear regression of the mean unit layer voltage measured at the nominal conditions divided by the current density (0.25 A.cm^{-2}). Figure 2 b depicts voltage of each individual unit layer. It can be seen that the stack voltage has a profile with the maximum voltage obtained at the middle of the stack and the voltage is downwards curved to stack bottom (unit layer number 1) and to the stack top (unit layer number 15). This is due to temperature distribution inside the stack as the heat transfer characteristics of the bottom-most and top-most stack layers differ from the other because of different conduction paths and view factors for the radiative heat transfer. The profile however stays nearly constant through the test period as can be seen from Fig. 2 b. E.g. at the start of the measurement period at 300 hours, the minimum, median and maximum unit layer voltages were 0.835V (unit layer 1), 861V (unit layer 14), and 0.871V (unit layer 10), and after operating the stack nearly 8000 hours, the individual unit layer degradation values varied between 0.31 % - 0.47 % with standard deviation being 0.045%. This indicates homogenous quality of each individual stack component as well as good assembly and manufacturing repeatability. The test period involves one load cycle 5600 hours in which the current was switch off from 30 A to 0A instantly and a full thermocycle due to scheduled laboratory maintenance at 7600 hours. Either of these interruptions caused any measurable degradation to the stack voltage.

Figure 2. a) elcoStack® average voltage in long-term test. b) Individual unit layer voltages in the long-term test.

Robustness in Emergency Situations

The typical weakness of the anode supported stack designs is the RedOx stability which is required for emergency situations. Typical emergency situation involves complete shutdown of all gas flows which may lead through diffusive leakage to a situation where oxygen transfers to the anode compartment. When oxygen is available in the fuel cell anode, nickel is oxidized leading to electrolyte and complete stack failures. This phenomenon may theoretically be avoided if the stack is protected by applying voltage higher than the corrosion potential. The corrosion potential of $\text{Ni} + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2 = \text{NiO}$ depends on temperature and is theoretically about 0.9V at 400°C and 0.7V at 800°C . The emergency situation also typically involves thermal cycle as not active heating means is available for the stack.

elcoStack[®] robustness in emergency situations was studied with cycles illustrated in Fig. 3 a. A cycle has three parts: (1) no gas flow or heating for 8 hours, 1V/unit layer voltage supplied to the stack, (2) feeding of 5 mol-% H₂ in N₂ to anode, air to cathode and heating the stack to 620 °C in 11 hours, and (3) changing the fuel to steam reformed natural gas and conducting polarization curve measurement with the steam reformed natural gas including stable operation at NOC for 2 hours.

The test system, stack and the reformat gas composition are identical to the long-term stability test equipment, materials and parameters. The gas composition and flow rate at the OCV conditions is identical to the NOC. 1V/unit layer during the emergency cycle was applied from an external power supply and the corresponding current was recorded. Stack temperature was recorded during the test with an in-stack thermocouple located at the outlet side of the active cell area in unit layer 8. Figure 3 b depicts the complete test run period with 15 emergency cycles. The test period included two longer periods at OCV conditions (190 – 280 hours and 560 – 590 hours) and one longer period at NOC conditions (445 – 475 hours).

The stack temperature was decreasing in the RedOx period (1) from 685°C to 420°C. As the cooling was conducted without a control, the cooling rate was continuously changing. The maximum measured cooling rate was 165°C/h. The highest stack temperature was measured at NOC. Changes in stack temperature between the cycles were within 5 °C but there was no trend seen with the cycle number. The maximum temperature at NOC condition is shown for each cycle in Table I.

Figure 3. a) One emergency cycle. b) The whole test period including 15 emergency cycles. Lines are the average unit layer voltage (black solid line), stack temperature (black dotted line), anode side gas flow rate (gray dotted line) and current (gray solid line).

The measured current during the emergency cycles is depicted in Fig. 4 a. The darkness of the line indicates the RedOx cycle number, black being the first cycle. The current varies between 0.15 A and 0.28 A depending on the stack temperature. The minimum current is drawn at 540°C and the maximum at 630°C. It has been observed in previous experiments that current is decreasing almost linearly from 470°C until around 300°C after which stack does not withdraw any current. The energy supplied per a unit

layer to the stack during the cooling phase was 1.63 ± 0.06 Wh. There was no clear trend that the energy consumption would have been changed during the cycles as can be seen from Fig 4 b.

Figure 4. a) Current supplied to the stack during emergency cycles. b) Electrical energy per unit layer supplied to the stack during the emergency cycles.

Changes in stack performance were monitored at OCV and NOC conditions. These results are depicted in Fig. 5 and Table I. The dark gray bar in Fig. 5 is the OCV value and the light gray is the NOC value. The OCV values were between 1.030 – 1.031 V while the respective Nernst voltage with the same gas composition and temperature is 1.031 V. There is no trend showing decrease in OCV with the RedOx cycles. This indicates that no gas leakages emerged to the stack during the cycles. The NOC voltage values varied between the cycles from 0.876 V to 0.860 V. The average decrease in the unit layer voltage during these 15 cycles was 1 mV/cycle. The decrease in unit layer voltage is typical in thermocycles for Elcogen stacks indicating that elcoStack® design can withstand even the harshest conditions of a typical SOFC system without seeing virtually any increased degradation.

Figure 5. Average unit layer voltage at OCV and NOC conditions as function of RedOx cycles.

TABLE I. Electrical energy supplied to stack during RedOx cycle, average unit layer voltage at open circuit voltage (OCV) condition measured with steam reformed natural gas, average unit layer voltage at nominal operating conditions (NOC) and stack outlet (maximum) temperature at NOC as a function of the RedOx cycle. OCV and NOC values are calculated as an average of from 60 min measurements.

RedOx cycle	Energy [Wh]	OCV [V]	NOC [V]	T(out) [°C]	RedOx cycle	Energy [Wh]	OCV [V]	NOC [V]	T(out) [°C]
0		1.030	0.874	686	8	1.58	1.031	0.867	685
1	1.63	1.030	0.876	686	9	1.63	1.031	0.860	687
2	1.59	1.031	0.875	686	10	1.59	1.031	0.860	687
3	1.59	1.030	0.875	686	11	1.60	1.031	0.865	688
4	1.61	1.031	0.871	683	12	1.80	1.031	0.864	686
5	1.71	1.031	0.872	685	13	1.71	1.031	0.864	685
6	1.65	1.031	0.869	684	14	1.62	1.031	0.864	686
7	1.63	1.030	0.870	685	15	1.59	1.031	0.863	686

Manufacturing Quality

The main stack product for Elcogen is elcoStack[®] E3000. This is used in large SOFC systems utilizing multiple stacks. An example of such system is developed in EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 671403. Elcogen manufactures stacks to the system and Convion Ltd. is responsible for the system design and manufacturing.

In order to enable successful fuel cell systems, the stack quality has to be constant. Thus, Elcogen is monitoring the performance of every produced stack with quality assurance tests with as high detail level as is still practical without increasing the manufacturing costs. Elcogen's standard quality assurance protocol includes current-voltage characteristics test and effective fuel utilization dependency test. Quality assurance measurements are conducted according to IEC 62282-7-2. Stack temperature is recorded with two thermocouples, the first located at the inlet edge of the active cell area and the second one located at the outlet edge of the active cell area.

The current-voltage characteristics test is conducted with 1/1 ratio of H₂/N₂ with constant flow rate of 122 l_N/min. Cathode side is fed with air at constant flow rate of 327 l_N/min. Inlet temperature for the air is 590°C and for the fuel 585°C. Current is increased with 1A/min sweep rate from 0A to 30A. The stack power is calculated as a product of the measured current and voltage.

The effective fuel utilization dependency test is conducted at constant current of 20A. The test is conducted at partial load in order to highlight possible differences in the fuel utilization dependency between the stacks. Fuel is 1/1 ratio of H₂/N₂, and the fuel flow rate is decreased stepwise 54.6 – 50.3 – 46.7 – 45.0 – 43.7 – 42.3 – 40.8 l_N/min. Stabilization time at each flow rate level is 2 min. Cathode side is fed with air at constant flow rate of 327 l_N/min. Inlet temperature for the air is 590°C and for the fuel 585°C.

The current-voltage characteristics test results are depicted in Fig. 6 a. The average stack voltage at open circuit condition of elcoStack[®] E3000 is 141.8 V with standard deviation of 0.5 V. The mean unit layer voltage is 1.192 V and the deviation per unit layer is 0.004 V. The average stack voltage at nominal current, 30A, of elcoStack[®] E3000

is 105.0 V with standard deviation of 0.4 V. The mean unit layer voltage is 0.882V and the deviation per unit layer is 0.003 V. The average stack temperature determined as the average between the stack inlet temperature (605°C) and stack outlet temperature (667°C) at the nominal current is measured to be 636°C. Stack power at 30A is 3151 W with standard deviation of 12W. The deviation per unit layer is 0.1 W as a single layer produces 26.5 W.

The effective fuel utilization dependency test results are depicted in Fig. 6 b. The average stack voltage of elcoStack® E3000 at 60% fuel utilization is 108.2 V with standard deviation of 0.3 V. The average stack voltage of elcoStack® E3000 at 80% fuel utilization is 104.5 V with standard deviation of 0.3 V. The deviation per unit layer is constant 0.003 V at these fuel utilization levels.

Figure 6. a) Current-voltage characteristics of elcoStack® E3000. b) Effective fuel utilization dependency of elcoStack® E3000. Error bars are calculated as standard deviations of the measured stacks.

Summary

Elcogen is continuously developing its unit cell and stack products to be more efficient, robust and affordable for different applications. Elcogen products are unique as their operation temperature is 600°C still being able of utilizing standard industrial materials and manufacturing methods allowing major cost reductions for the technology. This work summarizes some of the latest test results of Elcogen stack products highlighting the robustness, constant quality and long-term stability of elcoStack® products at the harshest solid oxide fuel cell system conditions.

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